

POLYPROPYLENE REINFORCED WITH CHICKEN FEATHERS

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SUMMARY: Feathers are a renewable fibrous raw material which is taken from e.g. chickens in slaughter-houses. Unfortunately, most of these 15,000 tons of feathers are not used in Germany but burned in combustion furnaces. However, these feathers consisting of ceratine possess interesting material properties which qualify them to reinforce plastic materials. The tensile strength of feathers can be elevated by heating from 130 MPa at room temperature up to 750 MPa at 150° C. For higher temperatures, the tensile strength decreases to 470 MPa. Thus, they are a suitable reinforcement for polyolefine matrices.

In order to prove the potential of feathers, material tests with chicken feather reinforced polypropylene (Montell XM 5164 S) were performed. Feather fibers were cut off quills and washed in ethylacetate at 100° C for 2 hours. The feather fibers were separated into downy feathers and tectrices. Both feather fiber types were mixed with polypropylene (PP) and bismaleinanehydride (2 %) as a coupling agent in an extrusion process at 200° C. The highest fiber (feather) volume content reached was about 10%. Afterwards, the extruded strands were pelletized. These pellets were further processed in an injection molding machine to produce dog-bone shaped samples (CAMPUS-samples) for mechanical tests.

Tensile tests, hardness tests, impacts tests, and heat distortion temperature tests (type D) were realized with these specimens. It turned out that feather fibers (both types) increase the hardness by more than 15 %. The same increase can be reported for the heat distortion temperature. However this reinforcing material brittles the matrix. The impact strength dropped of 50 %. Similar, the ultimate elongation decreases from 15 % for neat PP to 5 % for chicken feather reinforced PP. The ultimate tensile strength and stiffness do not change. The values of downy feathers and tectrices are the same but tectrices are more difficult to process due to their little barbed hooks.

Concluding, it can be said that feathers can indeed be used for reinforcing purposes with the objectives of increasing hardness and heat distortion temperature. It has to be taken into account that the material itself is cheap which could make it interesting for industry to use.

KEYTERMS: Chicken feathers, polypropylene, mechanical properties, coupling agent

INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

German slaughterhouses pluck 50,000 kg of feathers from chicken, ducks, geese, and turkeys daily, which adds up to $12.5 \cdot 10^6$ kg each year [1]. In the USA even $2 \cdot 10^9$ kg are plucked annually (world: $3 \cdot 10^{12}$ kg) [2, 3]. Most of these feathers are of no further use and thus burned in combustion furnaces or just deposited. However, chicken feathers are a sustainable, renewable fibrous material that can be used to reinforce plastic materials – a field which has only been explored by Schmidt from the Beltsville Area Research Center (BARC) in Maryland. He developed a strategy to use feather fibers in

paper formulations and for the reinforcement of polyethylene [2, 4, 5]. In Germany, the polypropylene is the dominant polyolefine for technical applications. Thus, it was intended to examine the microstructural properties of feathers, more specifically the properties of the feather's rami and the possibility of reinforcing polypropylene material with them. Furthermore, a method should be developed to provide a ready-mixed material consisting of polypropylene and feather fibers for injection molding application.

STRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES OF FEATHERS

Feathers consist of ceratines, which are horn materials consisting of peptid chains. These complex albumen structures cause the mechanical and chemical ability of resistance of hair, scales, feathers, finger nails, etc.. Ceratines are tough, ductile, but also hard and strong. They become formable under heat and can not be solved in water diluted acids. They swell in alkaline media and can be solved in sulfuric acids [6]. Ceratines can be classified in two types: α -ceratines and β -ceratines. Feathers and hair consist of α -ceratines, which have a helix-structure with a periodicity of 0.50 – 0.55 nm built of amino-acids. Hydrogen bindings exist between single worms of the helix. Three to seven helixes are wound into each other in α -ceratines creating a fiber-structure [7, 8].

Feathers used in this study are divided in tectrices, downy feathers, semi-plume, filoplume, and powder feathers. Tectrices are used for flying and consist of a central barrel and a sort of fabric with fiber like structures. The part of barrel between two fabrics is called shaft. The flexibility of this sort of fabric is derived by numerous rami or branches, which are small skewer-like filaments connected parallel at both sides of the shaft and oriented diagonally to the top of the feather. The branches are at longest in the middle of the feather and become shorter to both ends (Fig. 1a). Furthermore, the stiffness, smoothness, and strength of the branches decrease from the top of the feather to the lower end. Parallel rami are connected to each other by a high number of radii, puny secondary branches, which are placed on a ramus like rami on a shaft. A single ramus possess up to 600 radii leading to more than a million secondary branches for an entire feather. The connection between radii works mechanically by interlocking. On one side the radii are straight, while the opposite ones have little barbs which hook into the straight radii (Fig. 1b) [9].

Fig. 1: Tectrice (a), Interlocking mechanism between rami (b)

Downy feathers are designed for insulation purposes and have similar properties to tectrices at the lower end of a feather. They are fluffy, because secondary branches do not have hooks. Normally, downy feather do not have a shaft (Fig. 2a). The structure of semi-plumes is between tectrices and downy feathers. They have a shaft with rami, but the radii are without hooks. Thus semi-plumes are fluffy like downy feathers (Fig. 2b). Filoplume and powder feathers were of no use for this investigation due to their structure [9].

Fig. 2: Downy feather (a), Semi-plume (b)

It is obvious that an entire feather can hardly be used for reinforcing purposes. However, the fiber-like structure of rami suggests their separation from the shaft with the aim of their further processing. However, relevant thermal and mechanical properties of rami, the feather fibers are not be found in literature. Thus, feathers were conditioned in a furnace at temperatures of 100 °C, 150 °C, 175 °C, and 200 °C for one hour. Afterwards, four tectrice-feather fibers (length 25 mm) were cut off the shaft and their tensile strength was measured in a single-fiber-tension-tester with a pulling speed of 2 %/min [10]. Due to the ramifying structure of downy feathers, this measurement was not performed with them. The results of these tests showed that the tensile strength of feather increases until 150 °C. At higher temperatures deterioration processes provoke declining values (Table 1, Fig. 3). At 200 °C surface oxidation can be noticed. Furthermore, a reduction in diameter occurred due to a longitudinal, morphology-based elongation of the feather fiber [8].

Table 1: Results of feather fiber tensile tests

Furnace temperature [°C]	Diameter of rami [μm]	Tensile strength [MPa]
23	$57,2 \pm 7,3$	$129,7 \pm 38,1$
100	$38,3 \pm 6,2$	$307,1 \pm 98,9$
150	$30,3 \pm 0,5$	$778,0 \pm 79,1$
175	$37,0 \pm 9,3$	$343,3 \pm 63,5$
200	$35,8 \pm 6,5$	$194,4 \pm 62,4$

Fig. 3: Depicted results of feather fiber tensile tests

When comparing these values with those from standard natural fibers, it becomes obvious that feather fibers are in terms of strength equivalent to them (Fig. 4). Moreover, it has to be taken into account that the properties of natural fibers cited are measured at room temperature and decrease at elevated temperatures [11].

Fig. 4: Comparison between tensile strength of natural and feather fibers

PREPARATION OF FEATHERS AND MANUFACTURING OF SAMPLES

Due to the different structure of tectrices and downy feathers, both types of feather fibers were investigated separately. In order to be able to mix feather fibers with polypropylene, feather fibers were separated from shafts and cooked under stirring together with ethylacetate for two hours at 100 °C in order to remove the fat layer of the feathers. Subsequently, the ethylacetate-fat-mixture was separated from the feather fibers by using a sheet-filter. The fat content of the remaining liquid was determined in a rotary evaporator. It was 3.85 % for downy feathers and 9.09 % for tectrices. Then, the feather fibers were dried for 45 min at 90 °C in an oven to remove ethylacetate completely.

The polypropylene used was a Montell XM 5164 S-type with a melting point of 160 °C. 2 % (weight content) of maleicanhydride was used as a coupling agent. In order to produce polypropylene samples reinforced with either downy feathers or tectrices, two strategies were followed.

Firstly, a kneader (Haake Rheocord 90) was used because in this case the amount of feather could be varied very precisely. The kneading process was performed at 40 revolution/min for 4 min at a temperature of 190 °C by varying the feather weight contents from 0 % (neat polypropylene) until 3.5 %. After kneading, the hot low viscous bulk of molten material was transferred to a hot press (Collinpress, type 6200) and pressed with 50 bar (= 5 MPa) at a temperature of 180 °C to a flat “pancake” with a thickness of 1.5 mm of which samples with a length of 80 mm and width of 12 mm were cut out.

Secondly, feather fibers, coupling agent, and polypropylene were mixed in a single-screw extruder at a temperature of 200 °C. Feather fibers (weight content 2%) and polypropylene were fed into the extruder’s hopper by layer. However, due to the suboptimal feeding behavior of the feathers, the feeding had to be assisted by stuffing. The extruded rods were granulated in a crushing mill after cooling down to room temperature. Dog-bone shaped samples (CAMPUS-samples) with a minimum thickness of 4 mm and a minimum width of 10 mm were produced with an injection molding machine (15t-Arburg Allrounder) at a temperature of 200 °C.

MEASUREMENTS

The samples were used for different material tests:

- Tensile strength
- Young's tensile modulus
- Charpy impact strength, notched
- Heat distortion temperature (HDT)
- Shore hardness

The measurements of tensile strength and Young's modulus were performed on an universal tensile testing machine from the company Zwick with a maximum force of 10 kN. In terms of tensile tests, the previously mentioned specimens were tested at a velocity of 100 mm/min. The measurements in order to determine the Young's Modulus were only done on injection molded samples (CAMPUS-samples) because the hot pressed specimens did not have a sufficient length to apply incremental strain measuring devices. The pulling speed during this measurement was exactly 1 mm/min. The Young's modulus was determined between 0.05 % and 0.25 % of elongation.

The Charpy impact strength was tested at notched samples in a flatwise setup in a RayRan pendulum. The depths of the V-shaped notches were 2 mm. For these measurements, a hammer with a mass of 0.238 kg was used. According to the impact velocity of 2.9 m/s, an impact energy of 1 J was reached.

The heat-distortion-measurements were accomplished in a testing device from the Italian company CEAST. Due to the requirement of a minimum sample length of 110 mm, only specimen produced by injection molded samples could be used. The HDT-test itself is a three point bending test under increasing temperature transferred to the samples by silicon oil. The load was chosen in that way to subject the sample to a flexural stress of 1.82 MPa. The heat-distortion-temperature is that specific temperature, when the marginal elongation reaches 0.2 %.

Shore-hardness was measured with a Shore-hardness measuring device from the company Zwick. In this case, Shore D was determined with a needle (needle tip diameter 0.1 mm) under a load of 50 N. Due to the intrusion of the needle, only the thicker injection molded CAMPUS-samples could be used.

RESULTS

The results of tensile tests under variation of the feather content (pressed samples) are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Result of the measurements of tensile strength and Young's modulus

It can be seen in Fig. 4 that downy feathers possess a better reinforcing effects at lower weight contents. In terms of tectrices, the optimal weight content is about 2 %. However, a clear positive impact of the feather reinforcement on the polypropylene matrix can be stated. The results of the tensile tests of injection molded and hot pressed samples are depicted in Fig. 5 together with the Young's modulus. In case of the injection molded samples no positive effect of feathers on tensile strength and Young's modulus can be seen.

Fig. 5: Results of tensile tests and Young's modulus for 2 % weight content

The results of Charpy impact tests of notched samples are shown in Fig. 6 which correspond with those in Fig. 5. Feathers in hot pressed samples increase the impact values whereas the values measured of injection molded samples decrease. It shall be noted that the values derived from hot pressed samples are more scattering than the values obtained from injection molded ones. This is also obvious in Fig. 5.

Fig. 6: Results of Charpy impact tests of notched samples

The measurements of the heat-distortion-temperature indicate a clear increase of this value of about 10 K for both feather types in comparison to neat polypropylene.

Fig. 7: HDT-results

Furthermore, also the Shore-hardness rises due to the reinforcement with feathers in comparison to neat polypropylene (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8: Shore-hardness-results

DISCUSSION

The results of the mechanical measurements show that feathers can be used to reinforce plastic materials. In terms of hot pressed samples, the tensile strength was increased by a factor of 1.5 and the impact energy was risen by 20 %. The different results of tectrices and downy feathers are due to the very problematic distribution behavior of tectrices. These feather fibers are intensively sticking to each other which is caused by previously mentioned barbs. Processing and even more important temperature play an important role for the mechanical properties of feather fiber reinforced polypropylene. Due to the gentle kneading and pressing processes with low shear rates at adequate temperatures feather fibers were less damaged than happened during extrusion and injection molding at higher temperature leading to no reinforcing effect. As be seen in Fig. 3, the strength of feather fibers decrease immensely after conditioning at 175 °C or 200 °C in comparison to the values at 150 °C. The higher scattering of hot pressed samples compared to injection molded ones comes from longer feather fibers which were not as well distributed during kneading as in case of extrusion. However, the feather material ceratine itself affects an increase in heat-distortion-temperature and Shore-hardness due to its own hardness independently from the fiber shape structure. Thus, feather material can be used as a useful filler for plastics.

PERSPECTIVES

These results suggest to process feather fibers only at low temperature with low shear rates. Thus, on the one hand high-density- and low-density-polyethylene (LDPE, HDPE) as well as polypropylene with a low melting point of about 150 °C and a high melt-flow-rate (MFR, MFI) will be used. On the other hand a better feeding of feather fibers into the hoppers is intended. Furthermore, the possibility of reinforcing resins and thus lowering the processing temperature shall not be neglected.

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